

Synthesis and Structural Studies of the Complexes $M(NCS)_2(NCSTI)_2$ [$M = \text{Cobalt(II)}$, Nickel(II) or Copper(II)] with Ureas, Amides and Acetanilides

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Manuscript received 2 June 1984, revised 28 June 1985, accepted 29 October 1985

A new series of bimetallic tetrathiocyanate complexes, $L_2M(NCS)_2(NCSTI)_2$, where $M = \text{Co}^{II}$, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} ; $L = \text{urea}$, acetamide (actm), benzamide (bnzm), acetanilide (actn) and bromoacetanilide (Br-actn), have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, infrared and electronic spectral studies. These studies indicate monomeric bridged structure for all the complexes which is further supported by softness calculations.

In our earlier communication¹, we presented synthesis and studies of a new class of complexes, viz. $L_2M(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2$, where $M = \text{Co}^{II}$, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} ; $L = \text{ureas}$, amides and acetanilides. In this communication, we present the synthesis and structural studies of $L_2M(NCS)_2(NCSTI)_2$, where $M = \text{Co}^{II}$, Ni^{II} or Cu^{II} ; $L = \text{ureas}$, amides and acetanilides, in order to study the effect of change of softer metal Ag^I with still more soft Tl^I on the bonding mode of thiocyanate, stability of thiocyanate bridge and structure of the complexes.

Experimental

All materials and manipulations were as reported earlier¹.

Preparation of complexes :

$M(NCS)_2(NCSTI)_2$: $M(NCS)_2$ and $\text{Tl}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ were prepared as described earlier¹. $\text{Co(NCS)}_2(\text{NCSTI})_2$ was prepared by interaction of Co(NCS)_2 and $\text{Tl}_2(\text{SCN})_2$ in 1 : 1 molar ratio in dry dichloroethane by stirring the mixture for about 36 h. Firstly, the reaction mixture became dirty green but eventually a blue complex was formed. The product was filtered, washed with dichloroethane and dried in vacuum. $\text{Ni(NCS)}_2(\text{NCSTI})_2$ and $\text{Cu(NCS)}_2(\text{NCSTI})_2$ were similarly prepared.

$M(NCS)_2(NCSTI)_2 \cdot xL$ (where $x=2$ or 4) : $\text{Co(NCS)}_2(\text{NCSTI})_2$ (2 mmol) was suspended in ethanolic solution (50 ml) of ligand (8 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred for ~ 24 h. A pink coloured complex was formed in the case of urea while blue complex was formed in all other cases. The complexes were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by acetone and dried in vacuum. All other complexes were similarly prepared.

Analysis : The complexes were analysed for cobalt as cobalt anthranilate, nickel as nickel-

dimethylglyoximate, thallium as thalious chromate, and copper as cuprous thiocyanate. Sulphur was estimated as barium sulphate while nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Satisfactory analytical results were obtained for all the complexes (Table 1).

Physical measurements : All the complexes were practically insoluble in common organic solvents except DMF and DMSO in which they dissolved giving pink solutions. All of them decomposed without melting. Molar conductance values were determined on a Philips PR-9500 conductivity bridge. Infrared spectra were recorded on a SP3-300 spectrophotometer in the range 4 000-200 cm^{-1} . Electronic spectra were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss DMR-21 spectrophotometer in the range 2 500-200 nm. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were done on a Gouy balance using CoHg(SCN)_4 as a standard⁵⁻⁷.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results show that two molecules of ligands are attached to each molecule of the Lewis acid, e.g. $M(NCS)_2(NCSTI)_2 \cdot 2L$. Cobalt complex of urea had, however, four urea molecules attached, e.g. $\text{Co(NCS)}_2(\text{NCSTI})_2 \cdot 4 \text{ urea}$. The complexes are insoluble in alcohol and decomposed in water into Co(NCS)_2 and $\text{Tl}_2(\text{SCN})_2$.

Infrared spectra : All complexes exhibit a sharp and a shoulder band in ν_{CN} , ν_{CS} and δ_{NCB} regions in the ranges 2 120-2 135, 720-755 and 435-460 cm^{-1} , respectively, indicating the presence of bridged thiocyanates^{1,8-10}. Shoulder band is observed due to splitting of this degenerate band on account of bent $M-NCS-Tl$ bonding. A second strong and intense sharp band is observed in the above mentioned regions at about 2 095, 705 and 410 cm^{-1} ,

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complexes	M. p.* °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M.	λ_M M/512 $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$
		S	N	Co/Ni/Cu	Tl		
Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	258	17.92 (18.31)	7.94 (8.00)	8.30 (8.44)	58.24 (58.37)	4.32	30.28
(urea) ₄ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	216	12.95 (13.63)	17.58 (17.89)	5.95 (6.28)	43.22 (43.45)	4.98	40.53
(actm) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	223	14.52 (15.66)	9.54 (10.28)	7.02 (7.22)	49.54 (49.93)	4.48	35.63
(bnzm) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	226	12.86 (13.60)	8.39 (8.92)	5.98 (5.26)	43.28 (43.35)	4.35	35.83
(Br-actn) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	235	11.12 (11.35)	7.20 (7.45)	5.20 (5.23)	35.88 (36.20)	4.41	27.25
(actn) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	230	13.08 (13.20)	8.32 (8.66)	5.86 (6.08)	41.68 (42.10)	4.38	42.08
Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	220	17.87 (18.31)	7.90 (8.00)	8.40 (8.44)	57.45 (58.37)	3.00	50.05
(urea) ₄ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	248	15.18 (15.62)	13.21 (13.67)	6.96 (7.20)	49.62 (49.81)	3.21	48.08
(actm) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	242	15.42 (15.66)	9.98 (10.28)	7.12 (7.22)	49.60 (49.93)	3.12	44.46
(bnzm) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	250	13.21 (13.60)	8.62 (8.92)	5.88 (6.26)	43.08 (43.35)	3.08	43.76
(Br-actn) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	253	11.12 (11.35)	6.11 (7.45)	4.96 (5.23)	36.12 (36.20)	3.15	46.60
(actn) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	246	12.92 (13.20)	8.17 (8.66)	5.88 (6.08)	41.67 (42.70)	3.19	42.76
Cu(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	225	18.08 (18.20)	11.80 (11.94)	8.80 (8.96)	57.86 (58.03)	1.80	20.26
(urea) ₄ Cu(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	198	15.10 (15.55)	13.28 (13.60)	6.86 (7.65)	49.12 (49.57)	1.88	25.96
(actm) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	210	14.67 (15.59)	9.84 (10.23)	7.55 (7.67)	49.28 (49.69)	1.92	29.86
(bnzm) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	195	12.77 (13.54)	8.78 (8.88)	6.22 (6.66)	43.02 (43.17)	1.84	42.38
(Br-actn) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	190	10.55 (11.31)	7.20 (7.42)	4.96 (5.57)	36.01 (36.07)	1.86	41.63
(actn) ₂ Cu(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	175	12.96 (13.15)	8.50 (8.63)	6.30 (6.47)	41.80 (41.93)	1.90	35.70

* All decomposed.

respectively, showing the presence of S-bonded terminal thiocyanates⁸⁻¹¹.

In ν_{M-NCS} region, three bands are observed in the range 280-315 cm^{-1} due to splitting of the M—NCS degenerate bands¹²⁻¹⁴. The bands due to $\nu_{M-O(x)}$ are observed in the range 390-430 cm^{-1} . These bands are at the similar positions to those observed for M—L stretching frequency of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} or Cu^{2+} complexes. In $\nu_{TL-S(SCN)}$ region one or two bands are observed in the range 210-235 cm^{-1} . All ligands show features of coordination through amide oxygen.

Molar conductance, magnetic moment and electronic spectra: All complexes are blue in colour except urea complex of cobalt which is pink. Probably four urea molecules are accommodated by Co^{2+} due to the small molecular size of urea. In all other cases only two molecules are accommodated due to steric hindrance caused by bulky ligands.

Conductance values in DMSO (Table 1) indicate that all complexes are non-conducting. Molecular weight could not be determined due to lack of

sufficient solubility in the solvents. In DMF or DMSO, stereochemistry of the complexes is changed due to the addition of two solvent molecules.

Cobalt complexes :

Electronic spectra (nujol)¹⁷ of urea complex of cobalt show the presence of three bands in the regions 20 700, 16 680 and 9 000 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the transitions, ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_2), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ (F) (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) (ν_1), respectively. Spectral parameters, Dq, B' and β appear at 891 cm^{-1} , 842 cm^{-1} and 0.87, respectively. Pink colour, magnetic moment value (4.98 B.M.), electronic spectral band positions and values of spectral parameters indicate octahedral coordination geometry for this complex¹⁸. All blue complexes of Co^{2+} have the magnetic moment values in the range 4.32-4.48 B.M. The electronic spectra show the presence of two bands at 16 129-16 393 and 7 299-9 090 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the transitions, ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) (ν_2) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2), respectively, indicating tetrahedral coordination geometry around Co^{2+} . The spectral parameters, Dq, B' and β in the ranges, 424-499 cm^{-1} , 608-

TABLE 2—SELECTED ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL BANDS AND SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF COMPLEXES

Complexes	ν_2 cm ⁻¹	ν_3 cm ⁻¹	ν_1 cm ⁻¹	Dq	B'	β
(urea) ₄ Co(SCN) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	20 700	16 680	9 000	891	842	0.87
(actn) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	16 220	7 940	—	466	680	0.70
(Br-actn) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	16 260	8 438	—	499	648	0.66
(actm) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	16 393	9 090	—	545	608	0.62
(bnzm) ₂ Co(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	16 129	7 299	—	424	713	0.73
(urea) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	26 500	15 800	9 800	978	879	0.85
(actm) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	26 660	16 000	9 880	986	872	0.84
(bnzm) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	24 380	15 150	10 200	952	895	0.87
(actn) ₂ Ni(NCS) ₂ Tl ₂ (SCN) ₂	25 641	15 870	10 010	996	775	0.75

715 cm⁻¹ and 0.62-0.73, respectively (Table 2), also support this fact. On the basis of the above results and infrared spectra, following structure can be proposed for Co^{II} complexes.

u = urea
Fig. 1a

L = actm, bnzm, actn, Br-actn
Fig. 1b

These structures are favoured due to the following reasons: (i) presence of bands due to ν_{ON} , ν_{OS} and δ_{NOS} in the ranges of bridged and S-bonded terminal thiocyanates, (ii) presence of bands due to ν_{CO-NOS} , ν_{TI-SCN} and ν_{CO-L} (urea derivatives) in the infrared spectra at their prescribed positions, (iii) coordination of bridged thiocyanate through N-end to Co^{II} and S-end to Tl^I by HSAB principle²⁰, and (iv) softness calculations support the above coordination. Ligands are preferably coordinated to Co^{II}. Higher values of ΔTE_n^+ (Co-Tl) is obtained on considering ligands attached to Co^{II}. A higher value of total softness difference, $\Delta TE_n^+(M-M')$ in a bimetallic complex, indicates greater stability^{20,22-26}.

Nickel(II) complexes :

All these complexes are non-conducting in DMSO, green in colour and paramagnetic (3.00-3.21 B.M.). They show the presence of three bands in the electronic spectra at 24 300-26 660, 15 150-16 000 and 9 800-10 200 cm⁻¹ due to the transiti-

tions, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ (ν_1), respectively, indicating that Ni^{II} is in octahedral coordination geometry^{18,19}; Octahedral coordination is achieved by axial coordination through terminal thiocyanate groups of the second molecule^{2,7}. The ligands being harder than SCN⁻, will prefer hard Ni^{II}, and terminal S-bonded thiocyanate will prefer Tl^I for coordination^{2-5,20}. Bridged thiocyanate is coordinated through hard nitrogen end to hard Ni^{II} and soft sulphur end to soft Tl^I according to HSAB principle^{2-7,20}. This coordination of thiocyanate is favoured by the presence of bands due to ν_{Ni-NOS} and ν_{TI-SCN} in the far-ir spectra. Positions of ν_{ON} , ν_{OS} and δ_{NOS} bands also support such coordination. On the basis of these facts we may propose the following structure to the Ni^{II} complexes.

L = urea, actm, bezm, actn, Br = actn
Fig. 2

Copper (II) complexes :

Most of the complexes are greenish yellow in colour which turns brown on exposure to light. These are non-conducting in DMSO and have magnetic moment values in the range 1.80-1.92 B.M. Electronic spectra (Table 2) show the presence of two bands in the ranges 18 181-19 230 and 14 285-15 503 cm⁻¹, which are consistent with tetragonal copper(II) complexes^{7,21}. On the basis of ir spectra and softness values, we may propose Fig. 2 like structure for copper(II) complexes.

Conclusion : The nature of thiocyanate bonding is the same on replacing the soft metal, Ag^I, in $L_2M(NCS)_2(NCSAg)_2$ by more soft Tl^I.

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